

TECHNICAL CLARIFICATIONS ABOUT PASTURE IRRIGATION

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ABSTRACT

This article presents technical clarifications on pasture irrigation. Its scientific relevance lies in bringing to the academic discussion a subject that is much talked about and little studied in scientific terms, leaving many gaps to be filled by scientific research, based on empirical data. Its social relevance lies in making available to producers and technicians data and arguments that improve the search for greater and deeper clarifications in this regard. This is a bibliographical, exploratory research, based on reports collected in the field about the implementation, use and management of irrigation in pastures and, from this, a solid argument is made, presenting the benefits and risks of its use. Benefits arising from investments in the field of agriculture must be interpreted from the perspective of a specific science, Rural Administration, making use of precise economic analyses, comparing data and results. The conclusions reached are that pasture irrigation may even prove to be viable, as long as it is accompanied by qualified and professional technical assistance, analyzing and comparing costs over many years, requiring constant studies and a range of knowledge technician in different areas of knowledge, such as soil, climate, climatology, meteorology, animal bioclimatology, plant physiology.

Keywords: Pasture irrigation. Climatology. Rural Administration. Agronomic management.

INTRODUCTION

The irrigation technique is a very complex agronomic activity that requires knowledge in several areas, notably general biology and, specifically, the physiology of the crops to which

the procedure is to be applied, because numerous endogenous and exogenous factors are determining factors for success or failure regarding the use of irrigation on commercial plantations. As a rule, producers use the technique more based on common sense knowledge than on reliable agronomic studies and guidelines, resulting in financial expenses that cannot be repaired, direct losses and dissatisfaction, both with the agricultural practice and with the technician responsible for the assistance and guidance.

In the same proportion as one needs knowledge about the vegetable crops exploited, one must have considerable knowledge about the soil and its specific conditions and general characteristics, because based on such information, the technician will be able to plan the best way to apply the blade. water, the quantity to be supplied and determine the *irrigation shift*¹. This is because irrigation is a high-cost investment for agricultural properties; therefore, expectations of financial return must be in the same proportion for more.

Another extremely relevant factor is that each vegetable crop has a specific water requirement, varying according to its vegetative cycle, in the case of annual crops, and also varying according to the time of year, in the specific case of forage grasses. in which their vegetative cycles are directly affected by the photoperiod and ambient temperature.

In this sense, the option to adopt an irrigation system in pastures already begins with a cruel doubt, because given the investment potential and the possibility of economic return, the period of use throughout the year and the response conditions of pastures to irrigation , it is necessary to calculate the cost-benefit ratio regarding the investment and make the best decision regarding the most appropriate management for the situation. It must always be borne in mind that the agricultural property is a company and, as such, it must be managed. Each enterprise created within it has an added value and that, in turn, should increase the value of the actions undertaken there, that is, combined with the economic nature of the thing, there is the scientific nature, opportunity cost and net return on the operation. .

A big mistake that many producers and technicians make when planning irrigation systems intended for application on pastures is not considering the target object of interest, namely, the cattle that will use the forage produced. If it is intended for dairy cows, it is necessary to standardize the animals with the highest production and that are at the peak of

¹ The irrigation shift determines the frequency of irrigation and the volume of water to be replaced or stored in the soil. Defining the watering shift It is essential so that plant development is not compromised by excess or deficit of water . However, everything depends on the analysis of the type of soil, climate, plant and irrigation system used. The watering shift corresponds to the days of water reserves in the soil, enough to meet the plants' demands, without harming their development. For this, soil moisture must be equal to or greater than the minimum moisture determined by the soil moisture factor. availability of water in the soil (OLIVEIRA, 2024, sp) .

lactation, a period that goes from the 60th day postpartum, to the 120th day postpartum and these are the ones who must have access to irrigated areas . If it is beef cattle, the ideal is to allocate such areas to weaning calves, for the simple fact that feed conversion is better, due to the more accelerated metabolism, that is, with much less dry matter, there are greater gains in terms of net return on invested capital. The calculation is simple and logical: a cattle consumes around 2.5% of its live weight in dry matter (DM); therefore, a calf weighing 240 kilos of live weight will consume 6 kg of DM. An ox weighing 480 kg of live weight will consume 12 kg of DM and, it can be deduced that each of them will gain 0.5 kg of live weight/day, which means that the second animal, with a genetic characteristic similar, has a feed conversion efficiency 50% lower than that presented by the first animal. In genetic terms, both present high performance in terms of weight gain; But, it turns out that here we are not talking about genetics in isolation; rather, within an analytical standard in which food efficiency principles combined with economic principles are used as an objective response factor regarding a technical issue.

The aim of this essay is not for producers to give up investing in irrigation systems for their pasture areas; only that they understand that the results can represent a real failure, if scientific knowledge of many types is not applied, in order to foresee the benefits that may arise and compare them, technically, with other forms of management that have very good results and at a lower cost; because a pasture irrigation system never pays for itself.

THE BENEFITS OF IRRIGATION FOR PASTURES

The irrigation technique, applied to pastures, is a challenge that cannot be approached with naivety, as has been seen over the years, with producers repeating the same mistakes, without realizing that it is an investment and, as such, its use aims to generate an exponential economic return on the capital invested and, if this is not the case, the commitment is not justified.

By stating this, it is already in question that the benefits of irrigation for pastures are proportional to the risks, because the technician responsible for the project, implementation and technical assistance is required to have a range of knowledge and previous studies on soils, fertility and about the forage species used, in particular, about their physiology, in such a way that it can calculate the amount of water to be applied, the irrigation shift, the time of year in which it compensates, biologically and economically, for the application of irrigation and , even if such an investment will have agronomic support.

There are distinct benefits with the use of irrigation for pastures, notably the possibility of achieving higher levels of green mass and dry matter production, respectively, per unit area, throughout the year, through an extension of the rainy season. and shortening the dry period, in addition to helping to alleviate dry spells², a very common phenomenon in summer, especially in the central-southeast region of Brazil.

If the irrigation implementation and management project is well conducted, there will be a reduction in costs when compared to the need to offer stored food to livestock, due to the dry period; however, this offer will be for 2 (two) months of the year, at most, as there are no ideal climatological conditions in the center-southeast region, so that greater benefits than this can be achieved.

On properties that use high technology in cattle production (milk and/or beef), combined with pasture fertilization, the application of irrigation can become a differentiator, contributing to better dissolution of fertilizers and also maintaining greater basal tillering of forage grasses.

This issue is so relevant that Corsi (1988) reports that colonial grass (*Panicum maximum*) has up to 54 tillers per clump in the first week after cutting and, in contrast, has around 8 tillers per clump in the eighth week. post cut. This indicates that the ideal time to offer water, through artificial systems, to tropical forage grasses, is right after the animals have been removed from the mango, which would replenish the plant's water reserves, encouraging it to support the basal tillers. and facilitate its vegetative development.

A preponderant factor regarding the use of irrigation in pastures is the possibility of applying fertilizers via irrigation, using the fertigation technique, which results in a considerable increase in application efficiency, especially nitrogen fertilizers, which reduces application losses due to the high volatility of nitrogen (N_2). This agricultural engineering technique consists of dissolving fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides and other agricultural inputs through the water used in irrigation. This technique provides several benefits for the breeder, such as reducing labor, preventing soil compaction by reducing machine traffic and optimizing working time in the field. This practice will help to produce forage in a more constant manner, minimizing possible fluctuations in livestock production.

As has been discussed and reiterated throughout this work, benefits arising from investments in the field of agriculture are interpreted from the perspective of a specific science,

² *Veranico* is a common meteorological phenomenon in the southern regions of Brazil. It consists of a dry period, accompanied by intense heat (25°-35° C), strong sunlight and low relative humidity in the middle of the rainy season. In the Brazilian states of São Paulo and Minas Gerais, summer normally occurs in January, in the middle of the rainy season, lasting up to twenty days (Authors' note).

Rural Administration, making use of precise economic analyses, comparing data and results. Unfortunately, in Brazil, such data are scarce and unreliable, because there is a lack of long-term empirical studies, in which two distinct systems were compared for years on end, considering climatological conditions and the options that are presented to entrepreneurs and the attitudes they take in order to face the problem.

One thing is, in a period of intense drought, if there had been an irrigation system implemented on the property, many losses could have been avoided, because there would have been no lack of food for the herd. However, here is the question that weighs like a *Sword of Damocles*: the volume of water in rivers, streams and reservoirs would have sufficient volume and flow to sustain excess use, caused by higher than normal demand, when compared to years with normalized rainfall? Complex and controversial discussions; but that need to be put on the agenda whenever one thinks about the benefits of irrigation systems. The lack of rain affects an entire production system on a regional and not just a local scale; hence the need for a deeper, broader and more dynamic study when considering the idea of designing irrigation for rural properties.

One cannot be carried away by the naive idea that irrigation water replaces rainwater; the quality of rainwater is incomparable, because as it passes through the atmosphere it dilutes an immeasurable amount of nitrogen (N_2) and potassium (K_2), applying them to forage crops, along with other elements and substrates that are suspended in the air. However, one cannot believe that only rain will be able to perform the expected miracle, because it is not the way it is believed via common sense that things happen in nature. There is an entire physiological system of the plant that must be considered when determining whether or not to use irrigation, as long as you want to be successful with it.

On properties that have machinery available for making hay or for harvesting *in natura* fodder from a total area, irrigation is phenomenal, because it is possible to carry out up to six harvests or more just during the rainy season (October to April), still managing to have availability of dry mass for the off-season, taking care to choose an area with good drainage, high light, mechanizable topography and easy access. This becomes viable because after each harvest, water can be added, facilitating and boosting the regrowth of forage crops and ensuring a greater number of basal tillers, as they will not incur the risk of mortality due to water stress.

In ordinary cases, in which the use of pastures is intended for intensive herd grazing, there is the opportunity to provide gains in forage productivity, provided that appropriate management is adopted in each case, in particular, in accordance with the proposed work adopted on the property and the purposes for which production is intended.

If well applied, irrigation can bring great benefits to rural properties, in terms of meeting forage production, correcting intervals without rain, since these do not follow the same regularity that plants need for their full development. physiological. Of course, the vegetative benefits achieved with its use cannot be confused with economic profitability, and it is at this point that producers have made their biggest administrative errors regarding the implementation and use of irrigation on their properties. Water is an expensive resource and the producer must evaluate which type of irrigation system is the most suitable to be implemented on his property, after a detailed, sequential study. The first step is to check whether irrigation during the dry season is capable of significantly increasing forage production. For example, in places where drought coincides with cold periods, irrigation may not prove advantageous. It is important to know the water requirements of the forage on the property. Knowing the frequency of rain and the climate of the region also helps with irrigation design.

What must be very clear is that, for irrigation to present positive results on the property, the responsible technician needs extensive knowledge about soil, plant physiology and climatology, in order to know the demands of each of the elements involved in the process. Thinking about advantages regarding the use of irrigation in pastures is based on financial analyzes and not just based on the color of the grass, which creates the false impression that it is suppressing the absence of rain in critical periods of the year, in terms of the photoperiod. and plant physiology.

Tubelis (1988) advises that, in order to be successful in agricultural irrigation practices, and in this text the intention is focused on pastures, it is necessary to carefully observe the meteorology and this must “always be accompanied by observation of the organism behavior. This condition is essential to establish cause and effect relationships. Therefore, there is a need to note the dates and periods in which the phenological phases of the culture occur” (Id., p. 5).

In the case of pastures, each forage cultivar-variety has a type of vegetative behavior in which animal removal dates must be recorded to respect their mass production cycle, which, for most grasses, varies between 28 and 45 days between grazing. However, there are species that are very strict regarding these intervals, as is the case of the African Star (genus *Cynodon*), in which its protein content drops to very low levels in days, after the ideal vegetative cycle. Therefore, the determining factor for the success in the exploitation of such a crop would not be, exactly, the supply of water, but combined with this, theoretical and empirical knowledge about the physiology of the plant which, for its full result, would depend on very efficient management. .

In the same condition is the adequate management of the irrigation system and, “irrigation management constitutes a very important technique from an economic and environmental point of view in an agricultural activity. Through adequate irrigation management, water and energy can be saved, crop productivity can be increased and product quality can be improved” (ALVES JÚNIOR and EVANGELISTA, 2023, p. 5).

What the authors emphasize is that, observing the technical conditions for applying water via an irrigation system, there are possibilities of positive results and, what cannot happen is the opposite, irrigation is implemented on the property and then it will be worrying. to make it respond economically, producing results that exceed depreciation and maintenance costs. The use of the water supply technique, via irrigation, brings the benefits of increased productivity; reducing production losses; minimization of climate and meteorological risks (drought and drought); assistance in the application of inputs; increase in the carrying capacity of pastures; greater return for working with larger crowds . However, all of this requires meticulous assessments and situational analyzes carried out by competent and experienced technicians.

THE RISKS OF PASTURE IRRIGATION

Irrigation is a technique and, as such, its biggest risk is technical. This individual, when hired by the company to install an irrigation system on the property's pastures, must be, above all, professional and explain all the details involving the use of the system, from its direct and indirect advantages to the most insignificant risks, for the simple fact that it is a high investment with a long-term return and that it will not be used for many hours throughout the year.

Alves Júnior and Evangelista (2023, p. 1) argue that

The producer must do the calculations to see whether or not it is viable to irrigate pastures. In general, the recommendation is the following: (...) in a region that has a long period of drought (more than 4 months), and the problem is just water (high water deficit during the dry period), it is not short days (photoperiod) and low temperature, irrigation is extremely viable. However, in regions where the dry period is short, 3 a4 months, together with short days and low temperatures, and where irrigation will only increase annual forage production by 30% to 40%, irrigation will not be economically viable.

The authors draw attention to situations that range from climatology to the productivity of forage varieties and, in particular, tropical forage grasses, which make up the vast majority of Brazilian pastures, which have a very narrow range of optimization of their production capacity in the which refers to the climate, for example, the grasses of the genus *brachiaria*, present no maximum potential when temperatures oscillate between 25°C-35°C, where below

the first, there is a moderate 17°C-24.9°C and, 15°C -16.9°C slow development and, below 15°C very slow or no vegetative development and, at the other extreme, above 35.1°C, the plant paralyzes its vegetative processes related to growth and production of green mass, occurring in situations of days with very high temperatures, even turning the leaves inside out, as a way of reducing the evapotranspiration process.

It is observed that the use of irrigation in pastures follows scientific criteria, and operators must know minute details about situations that go beyond the knowledge produced by common sense. In addition to the fact that the use of frequent layers of water on the soil will cause greater solubilization of essential nutrients found in the upper layers of the soil, causing greater transport of them to deeper layers, sometimes at depths that crop roots cannot reach, which means that the producer must be more careful regarding the fertility of the soil under irrigation, with periodic analyzes to determine the acidity level and the levels of primary and secondary macronutrients. The analysis of the Nitrogen content serves to determine the crude protein content of the pasture, and once you have this result, the value found is multiplied by 6.25³ and you have the protein percentage of the forage.

It is important to pay attention to the fact that the crude protein content, taken in isolation, cannot be used as a reference to determine the herd's dietary management; This is about evaluating whether the management applied to pasture has proven efficient and to what extent. For more details regarding the feeding system and results, the alternative is to carry out bromatological tests in certified laboratories, where fiber content (FDA, NDF), digestible protein, micro and macronutrients, energy (NDT) will be measured.

The most promising risk with the use of irrigation in pastures is believing in the illusion that green pasture is sufficient to satisfy the animals' roughage needs. A cattle, considering one animal unit (450kg of live weight), consumes approximately 60 kg of roughage per day; Therefore, there must be mass available in the area to satisfy the volume of animals available there. To do this, the responsible technician must calculate the need for food for each animal and the availability of forage in the pasture and calculate the appropriate number of animals according to the data obtained; in other words, it is constant work and requires refined technical knowledge, at the risk of incurring losses even when applying high technology to agricultural production systems.

All of this that was explained above is called *management* . AND,

³For every 100 g of protein, there are 16 g of Nitrogen (N); Therefore, to define the crude protein content of a food, simply multiply the N value found in the sample by the constant 6.25 (100/16).

One of the main causes of the failure of many irrigation projects has been the lack of adequate management. Generally, due to lack of knowledge or lack of technical assistance or both factors, the producer or irrigator never gives much importance to this practice. The correct management of irrigation, to obtain economically viable productivity, would be one in which water is applied to the soil, at the right time and in sufficient quantities to meet the water needs of the crop, without lack or waste of energy (ALVES JÚNIOR and EVANGELISTA, 2023, p. 5).

To properly manage the irrigation system, you must have technical knowledge, something rare in rural areas, because most people talk about their experiences and boast about what they see and take for granted. Thus, many producers implement irrigation systems in their pasture areas following the fashion and wonderful advertisements they see on different channels.

The intention with any system is to increase production combined with a direct reduction in production costs, which is not always possible; However, it may happen that, even if there is a direct increase in production costs, the direct increase in the volume produced may, in the end, allow the acquisition of profits, which is understood as investment and net return on it. However, to reach such an assessment, it is necessary to prepare a careful spreadsheet, which describes every detail of what was applied and what was achieved, including predicting possible changes in the fees charged and the opportunity costs included in the activity. For example, what if, instead of irrigating the pasture throughout the year, this investment was not applied to silage production or sugar cane production, as a way of supplementing food during the winter period.

This is a technical and economic decision, not just one of opinion or discretion. However, to guarantee maximum security in decision-making, agronomic research in the field of irrigation should prove to be more efficient and more incisive in carrying out field experiments. The way the subject has been treated, where there aren't many long-lasting and reliable results, we end up stuck with different opinions and the answer is always that we do *not want to risk it or pay to see it*.

It is necessary to carry out field trials over at least 3 years, with records of pasture productivity, in different climatic situations and under management conducted within all recommended agronomic precepts, because this would serve as a determining parameter in any technical consultancy situation and even when carrying out a prior assessment for implementation on a property.

The risks inherent to any undertaking must be known before its implementation, not as a consequence of lack of knowledge about the object. If this happens, there is a situation of

economic suicide, which leads to harmful effects on the entire production chain. Therefore, when thinking about installing irrigation in pastures, it is necessary to consider that trees cannot be located in the middle of the areas, because this interferes with the uniform distribution of the water layer over the forage crops and, in this regard, it remains to be seen what matters most to the producer, whether the forage grass, whether the zoothermal comfort of his herd. Which of the two will bring greater direct benefits to animal production and profits to the property.

No technique produces miracles; produces results and, after these are computed and analyzed, one is certain whether they were positive or negative, which, in rural areas, is always unknown, because many producers insist on not admitting that their ventures are true failures or that the results achieved do not meet the desire for economy. Green grass is nothing more than green grass; does not indicate volume and quality in the necessary measures required by animals at each physiological stage they are in. If rain, alone, was capable of solving all the production problems of agricultural properties throughout the year, all the effort in technical research, ranging from nutrition, clinical, physiopathology, soil, climate would be unnecessary. Water is a vital component of the entire organic-metabolic process of plants; However, it is not the sovereign *measure* of profitability in an agricultural production system.

In this sense, Ritcher (2012) argues that,

Irrigation is cutting-edge technology: it requires not only a high-quality set to be applied, but mainly technical knowledge on the part of those who apply it. Sometimes the most important thing is not investing in equipment, but in people. No technology works if those who apply it do not have the necessary qualifications. This qualification must be sought from the person who provided the equipment, or from rural extension bodies, offices or teaching and research institutions. Unfortunately, in Brazil, more than 90% of rural producers who use irrigation still use the boot toe method to determine when to irrigate. For those who don't know it, it involves giving the soil a gentle pat, and if it raises dust, it's time to irrigate. This practice normally leads to the application of irrigation sheets when they were not necessary, with a consequent increase in water and energy consumption and greater wear and tear on the set due to increased use. This evaluation error is due to the fact that the 'method' only evaluates the moisture content at the surface, which dries out much more quickly than the soil profile at depth. For perennial pastures, which usually have deeper and more branched root systems than annual crops, it is very important to consider the moisture profile in depth to avoid unnecessary losses" (RITCHER, 2012, p. 501).

The author's speech reiterates everything that has already been defended throughout this work, that technical knowledge and appropriate instruments are needed to measure the determinants regarding the application of irrigation on pastures or not and when to do it, how to do it. Unfortunately, at the property level, things are done based on *guesswork* and the

experience (sic) that each person has about the thing itself, which leads to negative effects and disillusionment regarding technologies.

When stating that irrigation is a *cutting-edge technology*, it is already clear that the biggest investment to be made is the professionalization of system operators, because not only the culture, animals, soil, but also the factor time, a vital element to be considered when determining irrigation shifts and the return of water depth application after rainfall in the region. Another detail is that *a rain forecast is not an occurrence of rain* and many producers rely on meteorological forecasts and miss the windows of opportunity and phenological and physiological requirements of the cultivated cultivars, resulting in significant reductions in agricultural productivity.

Alves Júnior and Evangelista (2023, p. 10) argue that, “because it is a technique that began to be developed without the foundation of research, it has been perfected by [themselves] producers through trials (errors and successes)”, which seems to be a somewhat strange statement, because, *as a rule*, they do not know what is right or what is wrong to do; therefore, they cannot improve that over which they do not have any type of epistemic, scientific control that can support their practice. Cutting-edge technology requires investments in research, also cutting-edge, with results that are precise and capable of determining decision-making with absolute guarantee on the investment in terms of return time on invested capital and even the training of personnel to apply it. the technique, make records and analyze them. Soil care is extremely necessary, because with the increase in leaching, fertility tends to be a determining factor in the success or failure of the use of irrigation in pastures.

Knowing the texture of the soil is also extremely necessary, because soils with a higher clay content tend to retain more water and suffer less from the leaching of nutrients, while sandy soils are more prone to the transport of elements to lower layers. Topography will interfere when planning, requiring erosion containment barriers. In the end, knowledge or lack thereof is the determining factor regarding the economic viability of using irrigation in pastures.

Ritcher (2012) once again states that,

The practice of irrigation must always prioritize two objectives: that it is effective and efficient. Effective irrigation produces the desired response at harvest time. Efficient irrigation makes the best possible use of available water. Effective and efficient irrigation is the result of knowing when to irrigate, how much to irrigate, and how to irrigate. When to irrigate is an agronomic decision, based on soil and crop characteristics. When irrigating, the application of the blade is necessary to replace the soil moisture deficit at the effective depth of the root system. To do this, it is necessary to calculate the amount of water needed to return soil moisture to field capacity. How to irrigate is knowing how to apply water evenly (a high uniformity of

distribution), with control of the total application (a high efficiency of irrigation) (RICHTER, 2001, p. 502).

Once again, it is reiterated that the practice of irrigation applied to pastures can be a factor in improving production conditions; However, a series of details must be observed in order to obtain positive results and the expected profitability. Many accessory resources need to be added to irrigated areas, such as marginal shading, so that the herd can take refuge in the hottest hours of the day, choice of the variety with the greatest potential for green mass/dry matter production, choice of animals with the best capacity for food conversion to have primary access to the areas and have enough cattle to carry out second grazing, avoiding situations of undergrazing, at the same time optimizing the potential and economic use of areas that are under irrigation systems. It is noted that all the work requires intense dedication and improvement in management, both of irrigation and of the herd.

CONCLUSION

In this article, the issue of irrigation in pastures was discussed and throughout it, we sought to address the issue in the most technical way possible, clarifying that, as it is a cutting-edge technology, its implementation on properties must follow criteria strictly scientific, in which we seek to know every detail involved in the project, in order to determine its economic viability or not.

As advantages, there is an improvement in food production and, even in quantity for critical periods of the year, an increase in animal stocking rates, possibilities of facing dry spells without production and planning being harmed. For each of these positive situations, the necessary range of knowledge is required from the responsible technicians, producers and operators of the systems.

We tried to clarify that irrigation does not mean replacing the rainfall regime and, much less, it can be used throughout the year without interruptions, because the physiology of tropical forage crops and the photoperiod in certain seasons of the year compromise their full development. and what you have is green pasture; however, without a mass volume that economically justifies all the direct and indirect expenditure on equipment and action.

If adequate pasture management is not used, in terms of fertilization, profile fertility correction, in a short time, even under irrigation conditions, there is a risk of losing productivity and, consequently, the carrying capacity animals from them decay, due to accentuated losses through leaching. Therefore, much needs to be developed in terms of

research and production of technical knowledge, so that useful recommendations can be made regarding irrigation on pastures. The data that is available is still incipient to guarantee previous results and safe guidance for producers who wish to implement it on their properties.

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